

Role of National Education Policy (NEP - 2020) for Language Standardization of Linguistic Minorities in India

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Abstract

It has been established that the inclusion of the mother tongue plays a very important role for the children of minority groups in terms of cognitive and academic excellence. Conversely, due to their non-dominant status, minority languages are hardly used in the educational system, administration, media or courts. A lot of work has been done for the identification of the linguistic rights of minority languages. Benedikter says that Education should help the student to develop the necessary skills such as linguistic competence for partaking and involvement in the administrative process of nation building. So, use of language in education and administration should be attuned with each other. If the language of education acts as a counterpoise to the language of administration, it may create tensions which may frustrate the entire planning. A guideline in the light of the National Education Policy (2020) has replaced the 34-year-old policy of education in 1986. However, the absence of comprehensively agreed linguistic rights of the people, apart from the political and social dilemmas is used as an excuse for the failure of most state governments to recognize and respect linguistic rights of the minorities. The present study is an attempt to analyze the linguistic rights of minority groups vis-a-vis the Indian Constitution and the newly framed National Education Policy (2020). The study aims to find the place and role of minority languages in educational and socio-cultural settings. The study will explain the purpose of standardization of minority languages namely the Gojri language and the challenges related to standardization of minority languages which are being subjugated at every front by the dominant languages.

Keywords: Linguistic Rights, Linguistic Minorities, National Educational Policy, Language Planning, Indian Constitution.

1. Introduction

“The creation of national states forces standardization. The process of state formation creates the condition for a unified linguistic market where one linguistic variety acquires the status of the standard language.” (Duranti, 1997) Besides being a very important tool for expression and communication, language has a cultural value as well. The protection and recognition of minority languages and the identification of their linguistic rights have received enormous attention globally. Standardization is a process in which the language is standardized for its linguistic forms as well as the social communicative functions of language. Language rights are to be found in the freedom of expression, the right to use the language in the domain of education, and the right to use the language with others in every domain. The linguistic right means the right to use, to speak, to educate and to learn one’s mother tongue in every aspect. Several disciplines like linguistics, anthropology, language policy and planning, have contributed to minority language standardization.

Language policy and planning have given attention to the social realities of language standardization. The language experts are of the view that some policies are concerned with creating standards for minority languages also and National Education Policy 2020 (*Indian Constitution*) may be one of them. NEP-2020 stressed the usage of the mother tongue up to grade 5 in the education system of India. The right to use the mother tongue as the medium of instruction acts as a means to see how the education system can contribute to the identification of linguistic rights and accordingly promotion and protection of languages and their linguistic rights. While NEP- 2020 seeks to mainstream Indian minority languages, the communities demand more content, mainstreaming minority languages beyond communities, so that the children belonging to linguistic minorities should not feel inequality. The constitution of India provides educational rights, cultural rights, religious rights and linguistic rights to minorities. Article 350 (A) of the Indian constitution focused on the mother tongue at the primary level. It is the responsibility of the Centre, states and union territories to implement the National Education Policy - 2020 in schools, colleges, and universities. Education has to play an important role in the overall development of any nation or country. Schools, Colleges and Universities help in nation-building by providing quality-based education. The current study discusses mainly the rights of linguistic minorities under NEP (2020) and the Indian constitution.

2. Literature Review

Wardhaugh (2006) defines language standardization as “the process by which a language has been codified in some way. The process usually involves the development of such things as grammar, spelling books, dictionaries and possibly literature.”

Holmes (2001) defines standard variety as generally one which is written, and which has gone some degree of regularization or codification (for example, in grammar and dictionary): it is recognized as a prestigious variety of code by a community.

According to the National Policy of Education (1986), greater attention will be focused on the education of the minorities for promotion of social justice and equality. They would be helped to establish and administer their educational institutions, and protection of their languages and cultures should be ensured. The existing patterns of minority languages in education show a wide variation in terms of medium of instruction, subject teaching, level of education and duration of their use. (Dua, 1996)

Linguistic rights are in the hands of state policymakers. “Minorities, cannot take rights themselves just by proclaiming and exercising them. Linguistic rights need official recognition, instruments, infrastructure and funds for application, a secure and clear legal framework, need validation and support from the state, which exercises sovereignty and public power. Spontaneous activity in language and culture might be important as it is the speaker’s community to maintain and develop a minority language” (Thomas Benedikter (2009).

T. Schilling argued that ‘it is a characteristic of human rights that they protect nearly every aspect of human activity and human choice, and it, therefore, would be surprising if language rights were not so protected’. Language is for most ethnic groups one of the most important cultural core values (Smolicz, 1992).

Granting linguistic rights to minorities reduces conflict rather than creating it (R. Phillipson, M. Rannut, T. Skutnab Kangas, 2006).

According to Alfredson, of the UN Centre for Human Rights in Geneva (in a survey article on minority rights, their formation and implementation), it is governments who should be blamed for their reluctance to set standards for the treatment of minorities or to guarantee

them the kind of special protection that the position of minorities requires.

3. Linguistic Rights of Minorities under the Indian Constitution

The constitution of India gives its citizens various rights like educational rights, linguistic rights, religious rights etc. Indian constitution focuses on the mother tongue as the medium of instruction at the primary stage. Article 350A states that “It shall be the endeavour of every state and of every local authority within the state to provide adequate facilities for instruction in the mother tongue at the primary stage of education to children belonging to linguistic minority groups and the president may issue such directions to any state as he considers it necessary or proper for securing the provision of such facilities”. If a school is run by a minority group, it should get aid in the same way as the other schools of the state, there should not be any discrimination while giving aid. The schools must use the mother tongue at primary levels and should be open to the non-natives. But there must be some reservation for native students. The schools are not allowed to restrict the admission. Articles 29 and 30 of the constitution lead to the upliftment of minorities (linguistic minority, religious minority). The right of minorities to establish and administer educational institutions of their own choice carries with it the right to impart education to the children in their language and no authority can force them to adopt a language as the medium of instruction. This leads to the recognition of minority educational institutions. The recognition of minority educational institutions will accordingly lead to the usage of the mother tongue as the medium of instruction.

4. Linguistic Rights of Minority Groups under National Education Policy (2020)

The protection of linguistic rights of minorities has been discussed in the Indian constitution and time to time framed policies. Language policies explain which language(s) are/are going to be selected and standardized as the official language (s) of the state/union territory. According to NEP 2020, the mother tongue should be the medium of instruction as it acts as a tool to provide directions to schools and train young learners in their mother tongue so that it can improve their intellectual languages. Unfortunately, when India is developing and progressing, there are still a lot of things that are lagging and minority languages are one of them. Very few minority languages are taught as optional subjects. They are being subjugated by the dominant languages at every front. Mother tongues are defined as the language(s) one has learned first from his/ her mother’s lap and identifies with. Every child has a mother tongue. Mother tongue acts as a tool to connect us to our history, to our background. Every person must transfer the mother tongue from one generation to the next generation. Many developed countries have given the statement that, using the mother tongue as the medium of instruction is not a loss but indeed a huge benefit to educational, social and technological advancement. There are a few things to illustrate, one is the choice of language of instruction, the second is to teach the mother tongue to natives and the third is to teach the mother tongue to non-natives. Young children learn very quickly in the mother tongue. There are two types of minority languages some are fully deprived of their linguistic rights and some are enjoying a few of their linguistic rights. If we talk about minority languages, the teacher-student interaction will be carried out in the mother tongue only if teachers are natives of that particular language. Children of minority languages often attend schools where no teacher understands them or their language because it is not used either as a subject or as the medium of instruction. Schools are the main instruments to interpret, explain things and enforce modifications. When minority language is used in the education domain, it will lead its usage in daily conversation and automatically continue its usage in other domains as well. So, it will lead to the identification of that language. Naturally, people have

an extra attachment to their native languages, so everyone will welcome the use of their mother tongue in education, administration or other domains. Language rights can unite societies whereas violation of linguistic rights whether majority language rights or minority language rights, leads to conflicts.

4.1 The Linguistic Profile of Gojri

According to Grierson (1905), Gojri resembles Mewati which is a dialect of Rajasthan (LSI IX:10,925). Bailey (1903) opines that Gojri is similar to Mewari. Mewari and Mewati are dialects of Rajistani. Rajastani is a central Indo-Aryan language, so, based on similarities, Gojri has been grouped into the Central Indo-Aryan language group.

5. Objectives of the Present Work

To study and analyze the linguistic rights of the Gojri language in favour of Gujjar Tribals settled in the Shopian area in Jammu and Kashmir.

6. Methodology

The present study will involve the analytical and statistical approach. The current study includes primary data. For collecting the primary data, a questionnaire was developed and 31 participants were selected. The questionnaire was filled out by these 31 participants who were native speakers of the Gojri language. These participants were divided into three groups according to their age groups: Group A (10-15 years), Group B (25-40 years), and C (above 50 years).

7. Analysis

Gujjars and Bakerwals both speak the Gojri language and have little variations like variations in tone, mannerisms, and symbolic meaning of things. Through contact with and influence by different languages like Urdu, English, and Kashmiri, the linguistic forms of these people have changed a lot. The textbooks available for primary and secondary schools are available in English and Urdu language. Non-native teachers also use English or Urdu language as the medium of instruction. The NEP-2020 is being termed as anticipatory and aims to restructure the status of minority languages and ensure the progress of India more comprehensively. Standardization of minority languages has been a major demand of the people who speak them. An important aspect of NEP-2020 is the identification and support of students of minorities. It is expected that the adoption of standards for minority languages would be set only after consulting the linguistic minorities across the country so that no one will be ignored or left behind. While focusing on language standardization of minority languages, the writing system of the particular language may be developed and working on grammar, identifying the vocabulary of the particular language, and its usage in every domain will change the status of that particular language

8. Thirty-One Participants of 3 different Age Groups

8.1 Group A: 10-15 years

The analysis of the data is given below in Fig. 1 (a), 1 (b) 1 (c) & 1 (d). The statistical analysis depicts that the Gojri is preferred for all the social situations with all the age groups.

Fig. 1 (a). Interaction of Group A with their Grand Parents

Fig. 1 (b). Interaction of Group A with their Parents

Fig. 1 (c). Interaction of Group A with their Neighbors

Fig. 1 (d). Interaction of Group A in the School

8.2. Group B: 25-40 Years

The analysis of the data is given below in figures. The figures 2 (a), 2 (b) 2 (c) depict that the Gojri is preferred for all the social situations with all the age groups. The highest bar represents preference of Gojri language.

Fig. 2 (a) Interaction of Group B with their Parents

Fig. 2 (b) Interaction of Group B with their Neighbors

Fig. 2 (c). Interaction of Group B with their Children

8.3. Group C: Above 50 years

In the analysis of data collected from Group C, the language of interest for communication of the elder generation above 50 is Gojri. The analysis of the data is given below in figures 3 (a), 3 (b) 3 (c). The figures depict that the Gojri is preferred for all the social situations with all the age groups. The highest bar represents the use of Gojri language.

Fig. 3 (a). Interaction of Group C with their Children

Fig. 3 (b). Interaction of Group C with their Grandchildren

Fig. 3 (c). Interaction of Group C with their Neighbors

9. Discussion

The primary data was collected from 31 participants speaking the Gojri language from the districts of Shopian, Jammu and Kashmir. Among them, most participants prefer to use the Gojri language at home, with their family. They want Gojri programmes to be telecasted. The Gojri speakers want their language to be officially recognized. They insist on using the Gojri language in markets, at religious places and want their children to learn, to use the Gojri language in the education domain. But some parents prefer their children to learn, to use dominant languages like English, Urdu and Kashmiri in schools. They are of the view that learning the dominant language will provide them better chances to earn. If any minority language is used in media, markets, Govt. offices and education, it will lead to recognition of that language and with time recognition of a language will lead to standardization of that minority language.

10. Importance of standardizing minority languages

Standardization is a vital process in any language and developing a standard for a minority language has significance about the status of language and how the language users respond to the language. Language standardization is still an ongoing process for the countries where most of the existing languages do not have a literacy tradition, have no access to writing or have recently obtained access to writing. Language supporters and sometimes state authorities, view language standardization as a significant process to communicate through the mother tongue, promote education through the mother tongue and ensure better chances of success for linguistic minorities. This process requires choosing particular forms over others, developing and legitimising certain varieties of writing and speaking, and making structures and institutions that endure their distribution.

11. Conclusion

The study has focused on the mother tongue as the medium of instruction and linguistic rights of Gujjar Tribals. These people want their language to be recognized or to be used in every domain of social life. The purpose of standardization of minority languages in modern society is very necessary and requires conditions for the development of a standard language. The minority languages should be available in written form and should be used in formal situations like used in newspapers, and public speeches. It is time that the government should understand the gaps, problems and issues in the education system of linguistic minorities and should integrate the languages of the linguistic minorities into the education system. The use of minority languages in education will lead to the promotion of educational achievement of minority children. Gojri language is spoken in Jammu Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh, Haryana, Uttarakhand, Rajasthan, Gujrat, Maharashtra, Punjab, Delhi and other parts of India. By collecting data from the Gojri speakers of Jammu and Kashmir it is difficult to set standards for the particular language. Minority languages are not used as the

medium of instruction except very few. The government should take the initiative for minority languages to be taught as a subject, or as a language, in colleges and universities to provide bachelor's and master's degrees in minority languages so that we can get well-trained or special teachers for teaching minority languages. Appointment of special/well-trained language teachers and implementation of mother tongue as the medium of instruction will help the children of minority languages to maintain the identity of their language and they need not learn dominant language(s) at the cost of their language. Hence, by this, their mother tongue can be standardized and protected from extinction.

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